

SOCIETY FOR
HERITAGE
ARCHAEOLOGY &
MANAGEMENT

Journal of Heritage, Archaeology & Management (JHAM) Volume 4 Issue II
E-ISSN: 2583-4126

Biographical Notes

Ishorani Kamala Devi of Cooch Behar: An anecdote with Rajmata Uttara Devi of Kotah

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Accepted: 30 Dec 2024 / Published online: 31 December 2024

Image: Rajkumari Uttara Devi of Cooch Behar, Rajmata Saheeba of Kotah, Rajasthan.

Courtesy: Yuvraj Jaidev Singh of Kotah

Of all the members of Cooch Beharⁱ Royal family, very little is known of Rani Kamala Devi [Image-1] of Cooch Behar. The absence of written and/or published documents further makes it difficult to engage oneself in a research based on authentic data. With this lacuna in view, it was long in contemplation to gather at least verbal information on Kamala Devi from an authentic source. Thus, on the 30th March, 2018 C.E., I had prepared a set of questionnaires for Rajmata Uttara Devi, then Her Highness the Maharani Saheeba of Kotah, Rajasthan, daughter of Maharajkumar Indrajitendra Narayanⁱⁱ and Ishoraniⁱⁱⁱ Kamala Devi of Cooch Behar. The ebb and

flow of emails carrying question and answers continued till the 12th April of the same. In this brief period, Uttara Devi, not only answered the questions with heartfelt affection, but, also enquired personally, to her relations for gathering and validating some of the information in her memory. Thereupon, she also collected some family lore. It was difficult for her to write on her mother, since, on the email dated 1st April, 2018 she wrote — “*It is not easy for me to write all this. I was very close to my mother.*” However, she managed to put herself together and in some cases tried to answer as thoroughly as possible. This spontaneous overflow I didn’t try to alter and it has resulted in the accumulation of information, though in brief, on different personalities, events, places etc. related to our subject. Instead of intervening the main text, necessary information with in-text citations has been added in the form of endnotes.

I would like to offer my sincere gratitude to Uttara Devi for her time and effort. I also owe my heartfelt thanks to Rao Venkata Mahipathi Kesavachandra Rau, the Rajkumar of Pithapuram and cousin to Uttara Devi for his very kind assistance in framing the questionnaire. I would also like to offer my sincere gratitude to Bhadurani Bhawani Kumari Mahtab, the daughter of His late Highness Maharao Brijraj Singh and Uttara Devi of Kotah. Bhawani Devi is married to Maharajdhiraj Kumar Jai Chand Mahtab of Burdwan. After, going through the text she was kind enough to write a brief recollection of her own on Kamala Devi on the 17th July, 2024 by my request, which has been added as the first appendix of this writing. The outcome edited in the form of an anecdote, has been revised carefully by Uttara Devi, Kesavachandra Rau and Bhawani Devi, is as follows:

Q. When and where was your mother, late Rani Kamala Devi of Cooch Behar born?

Ans. She was born on the 2nd of October, 1922 at Pithapuram.^{iv}

Q. What were her parents or your maternal grandparents name?

Ans. My grandfather and grandmother's name was Maharaja Rao (Ravu) Venkata Kumara Mahipathi Suryarau and Maharani Chinnamamba Devi of Pithapuram, respectively [Image-2a-2b].

Q. Can you please share some information on your grandfather and his family?

Ans. My grandfather was a very learned man. He had written books in Telegu that were for years taught in Hyderabad University for M.A. He was a knowledgeable man in many fields. And it was in recognition of his learning that the British gave him the title of 'Maharaja', but, that title was only for him and not for his descendants. That is why the zamindars (of Pithapuram) before and after him continue to be Rajas.^v

Image-1: Ishorani Kamala Devi of Cooch Behar; early 1942 C.E.

Courtesy: Rajmata Uttara Devi, Kotah.

Images-2a-2b: Maharajah Venkata Kumara Mahipathi Suryarau Rao (Ravu) [1885-1964 C.E.] and Maharani Chinnmamba (1895-1933 C.E.) of Pithapuram. Till date there are two roads named after the Maharajah and Maharani in Chennai. These two roads are perpendicular to each other and are located off Mowbray's Road, Alwarpet, Chennai.

Courtesy: Rau Venkata Mahipathi Kesavachandra Rau, Chennai.

My grandparents had two sons and four daughters. Of their two sons, the eldest was Yuvraja Rama Rau and the youngest was Rao (Rajkumar) Venkata Mahipathi Surya Rau of Pithapuram [Image-3] respectively. Of the four daughters, my first aunt was Manjula Devi, who later became the Rani of Sidli (Assam) [Image-4]. My second aunt was Bhavyamma Devi, who became the Rani of Kotapadu (an estate in Krishna District of Andhra Pradesh adjoining Nuzvid) [Image-5] and third aunt was Sita Devi, who was married to His Highness Maharaja Pratap Singh Rao Gaekwad of Baroda, and became Her Highness the Maharani of Baroda [Image-6]. My mother was the youngest.

Our Baro Mama, Yuvraja Rama Rau, who became the Raja of Pithapuram on his father's death, had three sons. The eldest is the present Raja Surya Rau of Pithapuram and the youngest is Rajkumar Keshavachandra Rau of Pithapuram. My Baro Mama was a great admirer of famous Bengali men of those times, so he named his second son Ram Mohan Rau after Ram Mohan Roy and his third son Keshavachandra Rau after Keshav Chandra Sen.

Our Chhoto Mama, R.V.M. Surya Rau, was popularly known as 'Thammu', so we either called him 'Thammu uncle' or 'Chhoto Mama'!

Q. Where did your mother receive her education?

Ans. My mother's education was entirely at home, as were her sisters. The nuns from Church Park Convent in Madras (presently Chennai) would come to my grandfather's house in Madras and teach all the girls everything — English, Mathematics, Geography, History etc. The nuns were from Ireland and as a result, all the girls spoke excellent English and were well tutored in all subjects so that when they went out in the world after their marriages, they could hold their own in conversation in society. My eldest Mashima Rani Saheeba of Sidli became a Member of Parliament. My Baroda Mashima and my mother married into well known princely families and mixed with the best of societies.

My mother and her sisters grew up in *purdah*. They were allowed to go to the Ladies Club where they met other ladies from similar backgrounds. My mother learned to play tennis and this came

in useful when she came to Cooch Behar. They used to play simple card games like Canasta. They also played badminton etc. with each other. Years later when my mother went back to her father with Viraj (Maharaja Virajendra Narayan of Cooch Behar) and me, I went to the school (Church Park Convent) run by the nuns who had taught her. But, I attended regular school and was not educated at home. It was the best school for girls in those days and still is. It was situated in the heart of Madras and was next to a big church/cathedral — which is why it was called Church Park. They gladly took me in as I was the daughter of an old pupil. In my final year I became the first Head Girl of the school.

Q. Please tell us something more about your mother's interest and hobbies?

Ans. My mother liked reading, classical music from the South (South India), she was also an excellent cook in Indian food [see Appendix-II].

Q. Did she learn to sing or play any instrument?

Ans. She did not sing. But, she learned to play the 'Veena' before her marriage. I don't think she played while married to my father. But, after he died^{vi} and she was back with her father, she used to occasionally play with just us around, but not much.

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Image-3: Rajkumari Kamala Devi of Pithapuram with her second brother Rau (Rajkumar) Venkata Mahipathi Surya Rau of Pithapuram; late 1930s to early 1940s; Photographer: G.K. Vale & Co., Madras.

Courtesy: Rajmata Uttara Devi, Kotah.

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Image-4: Rajkumari Manjula Devi of Pithapuram, latter Rani of Sidli, Assam; possibly taken in between mid-late 1920s to early 1930s.

Courtesy: Rajmata Uttara Devi, Kotah.

Image-5: Kamala Devi (right) and her second sister Rajkumari Bhavyamma Devi (latter Rani of Kotapadu) of Pithapuram; late 1930s to early 1940s; (Photographer: G.K. Vale & Co., Madras?).
Courtesy: Rajmata Uttara Devi, Kotah.

Image-6: Kamala Devi's siblings: L-R: Kamala Devi's second sister Bhavyamma Devi (latter Rani of Kotapadu), youngest brother R.V.M. Surya Rau and third sister Sita Devi (latter Maharani of Baroda); late 1930s to early 1940s; (Photographer: G.K. Vale & Co., Madras?).

Courtesy: Rajmata Uttara Devi, Kotah.

Q. Tell us something about your parents' marriage?

Ans. Marriage to my father Maharajkumar Indrajit Narayan [Image-7] took place in Madras.^{vii} My Baro Mama Yuvraja Rama Rau, was a very sociable person and knew many of the royalties — big and small. Baro Mama, arranged the match as he knew the Cooch Behars well and knew my grandmother, Devima (Maharani Indira Devi of Cooch Behar), as we use to call her, was looking for a bride for her second son. By that time my Pithapuram grandmother was dead and so was my second aunt (of Pithapuram). [Images: 8-11]

Latter on, I also learnt from Kesava dada^{viii} (R.V.M. Kesavachandra Rau of Pithapuram) that the Pithapurams had Brahma leanings. Devima also had, as there were no idols or pictures of Gods in her puja room. It was a bare blue room where she would quietly sit on an ivory stool and meditate. I have often sat at the back quietly. The Barodas did not have this sort of leanings, so

I presume this influence must have come after she married Thakur Baba (Maharaja Jitendra Narayan of Cooch Behar). This may have been a reason why she chose my mother. I was not told this by any body. I have very recently heard from Kesava dada that the Pithapurams had Brahmo leanings, so I am presuming this. May be I am wrong. But my mother had no Brahmo leanings, she very deeply believed in the Goddess Durga!^{ix} [Images: 12-13]

Q. How was her life in Cooch Behar?

Ans. She took an interest in everything her husband was involved in. [Images:14-15] When they got married my father was in the army and fought in World War II. [Images: 16-17] She stayed with Devima wherever that was — Cooch Behar, Darjeeling, Calcutta (presently Kolkata), Bombay (presently Mumbai). When the war was over she accompanied my father to his postings in Ahmedabad and Lahore. Viraj and I were born and she was busy taking care of us and being with her husband. [Images: 18-19] When I was about three years old, my Baro Pishima (Maharajkumari Ila Devi of Cooch Behar, Rani of Tripura) died, leaving behind three young children — Bheem, Devika and Bharat. Devima brought them to Cooch Behar from Tripura and my mother was told to bring them up. She did that. She was a kind hearted lady and was sorry for the three young motherless children. She was also very fond of their mother. She brought them up until they were old enough to go to boarding school — Bheem and Bharat to Doon School and Devika to Maharani Gayatri Devi School (Maharani Gayatri Devi Girls' Public School) in Jaipur. All three of my cousins have never forgotten my mother's love and affection. So she had her hands full.

Q. How was your mothers relation with Devima and your Jethima, the Maharani of Cooch Behar?

Ans. She got on with both. My mother was careful in her relationships with her husband's family and tried her best to get on with everyone. She naturally saw a lot of Devima, respected her, listened to her, obeyed her and learnt a lot from her. [Image-20] Gina aunty (Maharani Georgina Devi of Cooch Behar) and my mother did not meet often — only during my school and college

holidays when we were in Calcutta and occasionally Cooch Behar. In Calcutta we were with Devima in Theater Road and Jethababa (Maharaja Jagaddipendra Narayan of Cooch Behar) and Gina aunty were in their house at Alipore so we did not see much of them, only occasionally at parties like on Christmas. In Cooch Behar we were not normally there when Jethababa and Gina aunty were there, so did not see much of them in Cooch Behar.

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Image-7: Maharajkumar Indrajitendra Narayan in a Royal attire; late 1930s to early 1940s;
Photograph by: Hamilton Studios Ltd. (Great Britain/Bombay?).

Courtesy: Rajmata Uttara Devi, Kotah.

Image-8: The groom and party being welcomed at the Madras Station during Maharajkumar Indrajitendra Narayan and Rani Kamala Devi's marriage, February, 1941 C.E.; L-R: ?, His Highness Maharaja Jagaddipendra Narayan of Cooch Behar, Maharajkumar Indrajitendra Narayan, Yuvaraja Rama Rau, Rajkumar Surya Rau and Rajkumar Gautam Narayan.

Courtesy: Rajmata Uttara Devi, Kotah.

Image-9: Marriage ceremony of Maharajkumar Indrajitendra Narayan and Rani Kamala Devi; standing behind Indrajit is Maharaja Jagaddipendra Narayan and the person walking past in a

dark achkan is Rajkumar Surya Rau (Thammu); 28th February, 1941 C.E., at ‘Gulabi’, Godaveri, Madras.

Courtesy: Rajmata Uttara Devi, Kotah.

Image-10: Marriage ceremony of Maharajkumar Indrajitendra Narayan and Rani Kamala Devi, 28th February, 1941 C.E., at ‘Gulabi’, Godaveri, Madras.

Courtesy: Rajmata Uttara Devi, Kotah.

Image-11: Maharajkumar Indrajitendra Narayan and Rani Kamala Devi; at the reception on the day after their marriage in Madras; 1st March, 1941 C.E.; Photograph by: G.K. Vale & Co., Madras.

Courtesy: Rajmata Uttara Devi, Kotah.

Image-12: Rani Kamala Devi (seated, left) engaged in a conversation with Maharaja Jagaddipendra Narayan (seated, centre); seated to the extreme right is Yuvarani Rao Venkata Vedavathi of Pithapuram. The photograph was captured at the lunch organised on the next day of Rani Kamala Devi's marriage; 1st March, 1941 C.E., Madras.

Courtesy: Rajmata Uttara Devi, Kotah.

Image-13: A group photograph taken on the next day of Rani Kamala Devi's marriage; 1st March, 1941 C.E., Madras: (L-R) :

Seated : Yuvarani Rao Venkata Vedavathi of Pithapuram, Maharaja Jagaddipendra Narayan, Maharajkumar Indrajitendra Narayan, Rani Kamala Devi, Maharaja Rao Venkata Kumara Mahipathi Suryarau of Pithapuram and Rani Manjula Devi of Sidli;

Standing : Yuvarajah R.V.M. G. Ramarau (latter Raja of Pithapuram), R.V.M. Surya Rau and the Raja of Sidli; Photograph by: G.K. Vale & Co., Madras.

Courtesy: Rajmata Uttara Devi, Kotah.

Image-14: Maharajkumar Indrajitendra Narayan and Rani Kamala Devi posing for a portrait; early 1940s; Photograph by: Universal Art Gallery, Calcutta. Artists & Photographers. 1, Cornwallis Street, & 180/1A, Rashbehari Avenue. B.B. 3078 (Calcutta) P. K. 2083. [Present

image captured from — Devi, Gayatri, *A Princess Remembers, The Memoirs Of The Maharani Of Jaipur*, 2015, p. 210.]

Image-15: A portrait of Maharajkumar Indrajitendra Narayan and Rani Kamala Devi by an anonymous painter; early 1940s. The portrait has a Persian inscription above which reads — Right band: “*Shabīh-i mubārak mahārāj kumār Indar Jitender [Jitendra] Nārāīn [Narayan]*”

sahib [Blessed portrait of Maharaj Kumar Indra Jitendra Narayan]”; Left band: “Shabīh-i mubārak rānī Kamlā Devī sāhiba [Blessed portrait of Rani Kamla Devi]”. I’m thankful to Somok Roy, University of Bonn, Germany, for deciphering the Persian script and its subsequent translation.

It is of note that, when asked about the above image no. 14 and other similar images and also the current portrait, Uttara Devi, in an email dated 18th September, 2024 wrote to the present Interviewer — *“The photographs were taken after their marriage, solely for the purpose of painting. They were not taken at the time of their wedding. Multiple photos were taken. One was selected for the painting.”*

Courtesy: Yuvraj Jaidev Singh of Kotah.

Image-16: Maharajkumar Indrajitendra Narayan in a military habiliment; late 1930s to 1940s.
Courtesy: Rajmata Uttara Devi, Kotah.

Image-17: A portrait of Maharajkumar Indrajitendra Narayan of Cooch Behar in an army uniform; by the painter Gopal Damodar Deuskar (1911-1994 C.E.); 25th June, 1949 C.E.
Courtesy: Rajmata Uttara Devi, Kotah.

Image-18: Rani Kamala Devi, 1940s, Cooch Behar.

Courtesy: Rajmata Uttara Devi, Kotah.

Image-19: Rani Kamala Devi in hunting attire, 1940s, Cooch Behar.

Courtesy: Rajmata Uttara Devi, Kotah.

Image-20: A portrait of Ishorani Kamala Devi of Cooch Behar commissioned by her mother-in-law, Maharani Indira Devi of Cooch Behar at Darjeeling; 1956 C.E.; it is interesting to note that, Uttara Devi, in an email dated 14th June, 2024 wrote to the present Interviewer about the portrait

— “...*The painting is nice to look at, but it is not an exact one of my mother. He (Ed. the painter) has given her high cheek bones, which she did not have. Many people in the east and north east have high cheek bones. I do too. But she did not. But otherwise it is a nice painting*”.

Courtesy: Rajmata Uttara Devi, Kotah.

[Note: Signature of the artist provided in initials on the painting cannot be deciphered yet.]

Q. The house in Alipore, where your Jethababa and Gina aunty used to live. Was it the Woodlands Palace?

Ans. No. The house in Alipore was not Woodlands. Jethababa sold the Woodlands property and from the proceeds bought the house in Alipore. The address was 4, Alipore Park Road. I have been to that house several times and even spent a couple of weeks there with Devima when we were on our way from Darjeeling to Delhi and then Srinagar. This Alipore house was left to Gina aunty in his Will. She sold it after Jethababa died, and went to Spain and settled down there. She died there in Spain.

Q. Besides being your mother and her Royal lineage, as a women how would you portray Rani Kamala Devi?

Ans. My mother was a normal woman who led the usual life most women of her stature with young children led. She could have refused to take on the burden of taking care of three more children as Viraj and I were small and took up most of her time. Yet, when Baro Pishima died and her children were handed over to my mother, she quietly took care of them. No one asked her if she would mind doing it. She was told to do it and she did. She obeyed my grandmother Devima. And she did a good job as all three of my cousins loved her. She had also been close to Baro Pishima. I will always admire her for this. Life was not easy for her with my father's heavy

drinking. He had become an alcoholic and often became violent when drunk. He had physically hurt her several times and she feared for herself and Viraj and me. Possibly around 1948 she finally left and returned to her father.^x She was living with my grandfather when my father died. [Images: 21-22]

Q. Was she present at your brother's coronation event at Cooch Behar?

Ans. Yes, she and I were both there in Cooch Behar for Viraj's 'Raj Tilak'.^{xi}

Q. When did she visit Cooch Behar for the last time?

Ans. During Viraj's first marriage, with Reena Sengupta.^{xii}

Q. Tell us something about the last days of your mother?

Ans. She spent her last days in Bangalore (presently Bengaluru). [Images: 23-25] Chennai is always very hot in summer, whereas Bangalore is always very pleasant. She liked Bangalore a lot. She had close family members there. She hoped to one day buy a property in Bangalore and settle down there for good. Whenever we joined her there for the children's summer holidays, she would take a small flat on rent and we would all stay there. When we could not go, like the year our son (then Yuvraj Iyyaraj Singh, presently His Highness the Maharao of Kotah) graduated from college, she would stay in the Bangalore Club. While she was there, she had a cerebral haemorrhage and passed away on 2nd July, 1987. She had gone there for a holiday to avoid the summer heat of Chennai.

Q. Did she go to Bangalore alone?

Ans. No, she was accompanied by a cousin of hers.

Image-21: L-R : Yuvarani Rao Venkata Vedavathi of Pithapuram, Kamala Devi, Yuvarajah R.V.M. Gangadhara Ramarau of Pithapuram and His Highness Maharaja Sir Pratapsingh Gaekwad of Baroda; photograph possibly captured on the 1950s.

Courtesy: R.V.M. Kesavachandra Rau, Chennai.

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Image-22: Rani Kamala Devi (seated extreme right) with Yuvarani Rao Venkata Vedavathi and Rao Venkata Mahipathi Surya Rau of Pithapuram at a jungle resort, Kambakkam; 1950s.
Courtesy: R.V.M. Kesavachandra Rau, Chennai.

Image-23: Rani Kamala Devi at the marriage reception of Rajkumar Kesavachandra Rau and Rajkumari Jaipal Devi; the reception was held after a day of the marriage ceremony on the 11th December, 1964 C.E., Delhi; L-R:

Kneeling : Rajkumar R.V.M. Rammohan Rau of Pithapuram; the little girl standing beside him is Kumari Anangarekha, daughter of Rani Manjula Devi of Sidli;

Standing first row : Rani Manjula Devi of Sidli, a family friend, Neera Devi of Jubbal, Rajkumar Virajendra Narayan (later the Maharaja of Cooch Behar), Rani Kamala Devi, ?, ?, Yuvarajah R.V.M. G. Ramarau, ?, ?.

Standing second row : Dr. Rangarao, ? and Rajkumar Vishy brother of Rajah P.V.G. Raju of Vizianagaram.

Courtesy: Rajkumar Kesavachandra Rau, Chennai.

Image-24: Rani Kamala Devi at a New Year's Eve get together, Madras Gymkhana Club, c.1965-1970; L-R :

Seated : ?, Kumarani Kannamma of Bobbili, Rajkumari Vimala Devi of Vuyyur, ?, Kamala Devi, Samarajyam of Mirzapuram and Rajkumari Jaipal Devi of Pithapuram (granddaughter of Sir Vizzy of Vizianagaram and w/o Rajkumar Kesavachandra Rau of Pithapuram);

Standing : Yuvarajah R.V.M. G. Ramarau of Pithapuram, ?, ?, Kumarajah R.V.G. K. Ranga Rao of Bobbili, Rajkumar M.V. Navaneetha Appa Rao of Telaprolu and Rajkumar R.V.M. Kesavachandra Rau of Pithapuram.

Courtesy: Rajkumar Kesavachandra Rau, Chennai.

Image-25: With the family of Rajkumar R.V.M. Suryarau of Pithapuram: L-R: Suhasa (Kamala Devi's niece or brother's daughter), Pradeep (Kamala Devi's nephew or brother's son), Gayathri (daughter-in-law of Kamala Devi's brother), Kamala Devi and Rajkumari Padmavati Devi of Pithapuram (Kamala Devi's younger brother's wife); photograph possibly taken on the early 1970s.

Courtesy: R.V.M. Kesavachandra Rau, Chennai.

Q. Who performed her last rights?

Ans. My Chhoto Mama's younger daughter's (Srimati Suhasa) husband, Niranjana Rao. I was away abroad as our son had graduated from college in the US and we had gone for his graduation. After attending our son's graduation in the US, we went to London for a two week holiday. We had many friends there. It was while we were there in London that we got the news of my mother's death.

As soon as I got the news I rushed back. No one knew where Viraj was. I flew back from London as soon as I could get a confirmed ticket to Delhi. The rest of the family followed soon after. They were all very close to my mother and no one wanted to continue with the holiday. I arrived at Bangalore two days later. I knew, I could not get there in time for her cremation, so told the family members there to go ahead with the ceremony. They managed to contact Viraj. He got there the same day I did. I handed her ashes to him. He took the urn, flew back to Calcutta the next day and immersed the ashes in the river at Calcutta.^{xiii}

Q. How would you like to remember your mother?

Ans. My memories of my mother are good ones. We were very close. She was a good woman who never hurt any one. Viraj saw very little of her. She left me whatever she had — which was not very much — furniture, some jewellery. [Images: 26a-26f]

Q. Were there any activities carried out in her name after her demise?^{xiv}

Ans. No, there were no activities carried out in her name. I know there was a school in Cooch Behar named after her.^{xv} [Images: 27a-27b]

Q. There was a Trophy in her name at Cooch Behar, can you please enlighten us about this trophy?^{xvi}

Ans. I'm sorry. I have no clue!^{xvii}

Notes: The information collected through the interview is verily a deposition of the simple life-style of Ishorani Kamala Devi of Cooch Behar. The importance of women education prevalent at the Pithapuram family, as well as the opportunity to avail themselves of extra-curricular

activities, depicts the enlightenment the family boasted at a time when such attempts were seldom encountered, even within many royal and aristocrat families of the Indian sub-continent. It also reminds of the home-education system, given the opportunity, which was quantitatively a common practice among such families. The Brahma leanings of the Pithapuram family, is a testimony of the far stretching influence of Brahmoism, even in a non-Brahmo family. This highlights the socio-religious plurality of the Pithapuram family and their contemporary cultural blending. Kamala Devi's bonding with Maharajkumar Indrajitendra Narayan, shows her dedication towards the relationship, however, gradually it ended up in dissention and finally, despair. But, even after losing her husband at the young age of about 28 (twenty eight) she never remarried and remained occupied with her children. Her affection and care towards the youngsters from the Tripura family is also notable. Kamala Devi's relationship with her grandchildren appears to have been quite friendly, yet, considerate. It is through her visceral capacity and skill, she maintained good terms with her mother-in-law, Maharani Indira Devi of Cooch Behar and her husband's relations, when in Cooch Behar and even after she left Cooch Behar. Her decision to will her assets in the name of her daughter, Uttara Devi, signifies her determination and unerring concern about family affairs. Kamala Devi, learning to play the Veena, tennis, badminton and card games, her passion for gastronomy, especially, Indian and non-vegetable cuisines, association with the Club culture, provides an insight into the interest, schtick and social-life of a women of her status and stature from the twentieth century. As per information provided by Rajmata Uttara Devi, the practice of letter writing was not popular between them, as they were already connected via telephone. Thus, while enquiring on Kamala Devi, letters or written correspondence, a source of primary information, are also lacking. Therefore, the interview recorded and the additional information provided by Bhadurani Bhawani Kumari Devi, are hoped to furnish primary data on Kamala Devi and her time, which will form a basis for further comprehensive study and research.

Images-26a-26f (top to bottom): A *Paan-daan* or Beetle leaf container used by Rani Kamala Devi (Image-a: Obverse; Image-b: close view of the lid after opening); Component: Silver; Dimension: $8.5 \times 6.8 \times 1.6$ mms; Weight: 78.30 gm; Provenance: Cooch Behar; Photographed on: 19th January, 2025 C.E.; the letters “ST SILVER/R” in two lines are embossed on centre of the rear side of the container (see – Images: d-e). Inside the container there is a fibre made

partition and a longitudinally placed rectangular partitioning bar on the upper surface of its centre. The partition is of the same oval outline as the container and with a dimension of about $8 \times 6.25 \times 1.5$ mms and weighs 10.09 gm (see – Images c and f).

Note: The *Paan-daan*, which is said to have been with Rani Kamala Devi till her last days, was gifted by Uttara Devi, to Mr. Nirupam Ghosh, when the late Maharao Brijraj Singh of Kotah, Uttara Devi and other members of the Royal family visited Ghosh's residence at Khagrabari, Cooch Behar, on the 14th of December, 2014 C.E. It was mainly through Ghosh's initiative that Uttara Devi's contact with Cooch Behar was re-established.

[Courtesy: The present Interviewer is indebted to Mr. Nirupam Ghosh, Foreman, North Bengal State Transport Corporation, Cooch Behar and Mrs. Manika Ghosh, for their kind permission and cooperation in photographing the asset; thanks is also due to Mr. Shantanu Saha, Photographer, for capturing the images and transportation and to Mr. Sujan Karmakar, Baburhat, and Mr. Ananta Karmakar, Chakchaka, for kindly providing the electronic weighing machine and required assistance. All of the persons mentioned herein are residents of Cooch Behar.]

Images-27a-27b: The former ‘Kamala Devi Girls School’ (estd. 1943 C.E.), now known as the ‘New Town Girls’ Junior Basic School’, Cooch Behar; 09th September, 2024, — above: main entrance; below: inside the school premises.

Photograph by: Rzishikalpa Paul.

End Notes

ⁱ The erstwhile State of Cooch Behar was founded by Maharaja Viswa Singha on about 1510 C.E.; it became a Feudatory State under the British rule from 1772 C.E. (5th April, 1773 C.E. according to another). [— Aitchison, C.U., *A Collection Of Treaties, Engagements, And Sanads Relating To India And Neighbouring Countries*, Vol. I., 1892, p. 99, pp. 103-104; Chaudhuri, Harendra Narayan, *The Cooch Behar State And Its Land Revenue Settlements*, 1903, Introduction, p. 3, para 6 and p. 2, fn. 89 of p. 245, pp. 245-246, p. 257; Ghoshal, Sarat Chandra (Transl.), *A History Of Cooch Behar*, 1942, pp. 454-469, especially pp. 454-466; Mercer, Lawrence and Chauvet, John Lewis, *The Cooch Behar Select Records, Messieurs Mercer and Chauvet’s Report On Cooch Behar In 1788*, Vol. II, 1869, Article 5th of pp. 184-186; *The Imperial Gazetteer Of India*, Vol-X, New Edition, 1908, pp. 379, 382; Low, Kt., Francis (Ed.), *The Indian Year Book 1945-46*, Vol. XXXII., p. 214; Banerjee, Bhagavati Charan, *History Of Cooch Behar*, 2nd Edition, 1884, pp. 42-43, 105-107, 117-119; Campbell, A. Claude, *Glimpses Of Bengal*, Vol. I, 1907, p. 284; Brahma, Kshetramohan, *A sheet account of Cooch Behar*, 2nd Enlarged Edition, July, 1917; Brahma, Kshetramohan,

CoochBeharer Chumbak Bibaran, 2nd Edition, Shraavan 1349 B.S. (July-August, 1942 C.E.), p. 2; Singh, Gurmukh Nihal, *Indian States & British India: Their Future Relations*, 1930, p. 5]. It maintained its existence as a separate Princely State till its merger with the dominion of India on the 28th August 1949 C.E. and was taken over by the Government of India as a Chief Commissioner's Province on the 12th September of the same. Cooch Behar ultimately became a District of West Bengal from the 1st January, 1950 C.E. [— *Agreement Dated, the 28th August, 1949 Made Between The Governor General of India And His Highness the Maharaja Of Cooch Behar*, also see p. 15, Article I.; *Government Of India Ministry Of States: White Paper On Indian States*, 1950, Appendix XLVI., pp. 309-312; Menon, V.P., *The Story Of The Integration Of The Indian States*, First Published: March, 1956, Reprint: September, 1956, p. 309].

ⁱⁱ Maharajkumar Indrajitendra Narayan, the second son of Maharaja Jitendra Narayan (1913-1922 C.E.) and Maharani Indira Devi Saheeba of Cooch Behar, was born on 6th July, 1918 C.E., 09:22 p.m. Calcutta time, at Poona [— *The Annual Administration Report Of The Cooch Behar State For The Year 1918-1919*, 1. (Report of the State —) Council Office; 1919, p. 3, para 12; *The Cooch Behar Gazetteer For The Year 1943*, 1943, p. ii, para 4; Devi, Gayatri, *A Princess Remembers*, 1995, p. 36]. He received his education at Gibbs School, London, Mayo College, Ajmer and Military Academy, Dehra Dun, India [— Devi, *op. cit.*, pp. 87, 109 and p. 139]. He was Lieutenant Colonel at the Military [— *The Cooch Behar Gazetteer For The Year 1946*, 1946, p. 1] and served at the Second World War [— *Cf.* — Devi, p. 153; also mentioned at the present interview]. During the State regime, he was the Secretary to the Government of Cooch Behar in the General Secretariat and Deputy Development Commissioner, Development Department, Cooch Behar State [— *The Cooch Behar Gazetteer For The Year 1946, op. cit.*, p. 4 and p. 57]. He served as the President of 'Cooch Behar Sahitya Sabha' (estd. 1915 C.E.) from 1939-1950 C.E. [— Sen, Subodh and Dutta, Gopesh (Ed.), *Cooch Behar Sahitya Sabha Patrika*, 27th December, 1991]. Indrajit died of a tragic accident at Darjeeling in 1951 C.E. [— *Vide infra en. vi*].

ⁱⁱⁱ The term 'Ishorani' or 'Isharani' has derived from the Sanskrit term 'Ishwarani', meaning 'The Goddess Queen'. Generally, the prefix Ishorani is applied to the women married to any scion of the Cooch Behar Royal family other than the Maharaja himself.

^{iv} The Pithapuram family is a very old Zamindari dynasty based on the erstwhile Madras Presidency. The origins of the dynasty can be traced back to the fifteenth century [— Hemingway, F.R., *Madras District Gazetteers: Godavari*, 1915, p. 234, for more on Pithapuram, also see — pp. 227-233 and pp. 233-239; Firminger, Walter Kelly (Ed.), *The Fifth Report From The Select Committee Of The House Of Commons On The Affairs Of The East India Company Dated 28th July, 1812*, Vol. III., 1918, Appendix No. 13, 'Political Survey Of The Northern Circars, By James Grant, Esquire; Transmitted by the Bengal Government, in the year 1786, to the Court of Directors.', p. 76.]

^v The following passage alluded from an account by F.R. Hemingway (1915 C.E.), offers a glimpse into the condition of the Pithapuram Zamindari during the early period of Maharajah Venkata Kumara Mahipathi Suryarau [1885-1964 C.E.] — "*The estate is a remarkably fine one. In the early years of British administration it was no doubt overshadowed by the more important zamindari of Peddápúram; but while the latter has ceased to exist Pithápúram has greatly extended. Not only does it now comprise nearly the whole of the Pithápúram division and the Cocanada taluk, but it also owns fourteen villages in Amalápúram, twelve in Tuni, nine in Rajahmundry, eight in Rámachandrapuram and four in Chódavaram, as well as others in North Arcot and other districts. Its total area is 383 square miles and its income in 1903-04 was Rs. 9,14,000, and the peshkash Rs. 2,44,000.*" [— Hemingway, *op. cit.*, p. 237.]

^{vi} Maharajkumar Indrajitendra Narayan died on the 04th April, 1951 C.E. at Darjeeling [– *Lewiston Evening Journal*, ‘Texas Girl Claims She Is Sister-in-Law Of Indian Maharajah’, News Report, Weekly, Volume XCI, Saturday, May 26, 1951, p. 8, Column 6; Devi, *op. cit.*, pp. 246-247; Moore, Lucy, *Maharanis*, 2004, p. 247].

^{vii} The *Upanayan* ceremony (the sacred thread ceremony) of Maharajkumar Indrajitendra Narayan was performed on the 16th February, 1941 C.E. at Bombay (presently Mumbai) and his marriage ceremony with Rani Kamala Devi took place on the 28th February of the same, at Godaveri, Madras [– *The Annual Report On The General Administration Of The Cooch Behar State For The Year 1940-1941*, 1941, p. 28, para 11; *The Cooch Behar Gazetteer For The Year 1943*, p. ii, para 4]. There was also large a celebration at Woodlands, Kolkata. Gayatri Devi (1995 C.E.), recalled in her memoir – “*The last big celebration we ever held at ‘Woodlands’ was on the occasion of Indrajit’s engagement to the Princess of Pithapuram.*” [— Devi, *op. cit.*, pp. 199-200].

^{viii} According to Rao Venkata Mahipathi Kesavachandra Rau, the marriage of Kamala Devi with Indrajitendra Narayan took place at the Pithapuram house in Madras (now demolished). Kesavachandra Rau, in one of his reminiscence wrote to the present Interviewer among others about the Madras residence and Kamala Devi’s marriage in an email dated 25th July, 2024 C.E. Since, the information is related to Kamala Devi and her family, a few lines may not be impertinent to quote — “*Madras (now Chennai) was the capital of the then Madras Presidency comprising of Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh, the Malabar of Kerala and the South Kanara District of Karnataka. Our Zamindari covered most of the East Godavari District of coastal Andhra Pradesh excluding the major cities. The seat of Pithapuram Zamindar was at Pithapuram Town, where there was a Fort. I do not remember much of the Fort in Pithapuram, a huge place with high mud walls all around the grounds with a mini forest within, the fort was seven stories high with several ancillary buildings. (...)*

“*Madras was a second residence. The Governor and the Presidency administration was at Madras. Madras offered decent English medium schooling, medical facilities etc. Therefore, many Zamindars had their second residences in Madras. Our residence was called “Gulabi” (Telugu word for a “Rose”). A mansion located next to the Adyar River on a 20 acre plot. The house comprised of gardens with Roses, Mango and other fruit trees. There were two large ponds with lotuses. A patch of land jutting into the adjoining river with lots of Casuarina trees. The double-storied residence had eight suites, two drawing halls, two dining rooms, a library and table tennis room. I was born here on 07th March, 1938 (C.E.). Princess Kamala Devi’s marriage took place at this mansion.*”

It is the same house which Uttara Devi has mentioned in the present anecdote while writing about Kamala Devi’s education.

^{ix} On 19th July, 2024, Uttara Devi wrote to the author in an email – “*I would like to add a few lines about my grandmother’s blue puja room. Some years back a journalist Amita Roy asked me if the Cooch Behar family were Shani worshippers. When I emphatically denied it, she said that the ASI (Archaeological Survey of India) people were saying this was so because of the blue room. I would once again like to strongly reject this theory. My family were never Shani worshippers. My grandmother had Brahma leanings, had her puja room painted a soothing blue, no pictures or idols of Gods and Goddesses, there was a big book in front of her which I always presumed was the Bhagwad Geeta and that was all, nothing less and nothing more. I have often sat behind her quietly while she prayed and meditated. So I should know.*”

The present Interviewer also heard something similar from an ASI Official possibly sometime back in c.1998-1999, which appeared to him nothing but a mere speculation borne out of the blue colour of the room. This conjecture neither hold any ground in the historical records nor in any lores of Cooch Behar. Thus, the theory as already stated by Uttara Devi, is undoubtedly repudiable.

The Puja or Prayer room is still there. It is located on the first floor of the front southern wing of the palace. It faces east and can be numbered as the fourth room from north to south. When back in 2014 C.E., His Highness the late Maharao Brijraj Singh and Her Highness Maharani Uttara Devi (now Rajmata) visited Cooch Behar with family, the present author accompanied them to the Cooch Behar palace on 17th December of the same. While visiting the palace, Uttara Devi was kind enough to share her memories of the palace, its rooms, purlieu and many others. She also physically pointed out several rooms, locations etc. and narrated her recollections which also included the history of the room under discussion.

^x According to an Agreement, commonly known as the ‘Merger Agreement’, Dated, the 28th August, 1949 C.E., between the Governor General of India and His Highness Maharaja Jagaddipendra Narayan of Cooch Behar, Maharajkumar Indrajitendra Narayan received an allowance of Rupees 36,000 (thirty six thousand) per annum of which Rupees 6,000 (six thousand) was to be paid to Rani Kamala Devi per annum, for the maintenance of his two children. The allowances for the children were to be discontinued when the daughter was married and the son attained the age of 25 (twenty five). [– *Agreement Dated, the 28th August, 1949 Made Between The Governor General of India And His Highness the Maharaja Of Cooch Behar*, p. 3.]

^{xi} After the demise of Rajkumar Virajendra Narayan’s (1944-1992 C.E.) uncle, Maharaja Jagaddipendra Narayan of Cooch Behar on 11th April, 1970 C.E., Virajendra succeeded him as a Titular Ruler of Cooch Behar [— Pal, Nripendra Nath, *Itikathay Coochbehar*, Corrected & Enlarged Edition: 27th June, 2006, p. 98].

^{xii} Maharaja Virajendra Narayan’s first marriage took place with Reena Sengupta, daughter of a Military Colonel from Kolkata on 17th February, 1973 C.E. It appears that Kamala Devi along with Maharajkumari Maneka Devi of Cooch Behar, Her Highness the Maharani Saheeba of Dewas Junior, Uttara Devi, then Yuvarani of Kotah (now Rajmata) and others visited Cooch Behar in connection with the marriage celebrations. [— Bhattacharyya, Tarun Krishna (Ed.), ‘Maharaja Shree Virajendra Narayan Bhup Bahadurer Shuva-Parinay’, *Nagarik*, News Report, Weekly, 16th Year, 20th Issue, 25th February, 1973, p. 1, Columns 1-2.]

^{xiii} During the period of Maharaja Nripendra Narayan (1862-1911 C.E.) and Maharani Sunity Devi (1864-1932 C.E.), grand parents of Indrajit Narayan, Brahmo religion entered the Cooch Behar Royal family. Since then, alike many other Brahmo families, after the death and cremation of a practicing Brahmo member of the family, their ashes were preserved in an urn which was interred and above it, either a monument or a structure usually comprising of a plaque was erected. The place more or less served like that of a cinerarium. After the death of Nripendra Narayan in 1911 C.E., his *Shradh* was performed according to the Brahmo rites following the “New Samhita” [— Sanyal, Sites Chandra, *The Late Maharaja Of Cooch Behar*, 1912, pp. 6-7; *The Annual Administration Report Of The Cooch Behar State For The Year 1911-1912*, 1912, 3. Revenue Administration, p. 14, para 59; Also see the discussion on ‘Shraddha-Paddhati (Nabasanhita)’ booklet in — Paul, Rzishikalpa, ‘Mudraner Yuge Cooch Behar Sambandhiya Aitihāsik Guruttva-smpanna Pustika – Nirbachita Path’, *Abahaman*, Vol. 11-12, No. 13-14, January-June/July-December, 2021-22, pp. 89-92] and a monument (“Samadhi”) was erected within the Cooch Behar Palace gardens [— *The Annual Administration Report Of The Cooch Behar State For The Year 1912-1913*, 1913, 1. Council Office, p. 6, para 19, 2. General Administration, p. 14, para 71(c), 3. Revenue Administration, p. 13, para 50, *The Annual Administration*
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Report Of The Cooch Behar State For The Year 1913-1914, 1914, 2. General Administration, p. 14, para 75(c), 3. Revenue Administration, p. 14, para 46; *The Annual Administration Report Of The Cooch Behar State For The Year 1914-1915*, 1915, 2. General Administration, p. 5, para 36(c), 3. Revenue Administration, p. 21, para 35]. Nripendra was succeeded by his eldest son, Maharaja Raj Rajendra Narayan and after Raj Rajendra's demise in 1913 C.E., similarly a monument was erected in his memory [— *The Annual Administration Report Of The Cooch Behar State For The Year 1914-1915*, *op. cit.*, 2. General Administration, p. 5, para 36(d); *The Annual Administration Report Of the Cooch Behar State For The Year 1915-1916*, 1917, 2. General Administration, p. 24, para 98; *The Annual Administration Report Of the Cooch Behar State For The Year 1916-1917*, 1917, 2. General Administration, p. 28, para 111]. However, after the death of Raj Rajendra's brother, who succeeded him as the next ruler, Maharaja Jitendra Narayan in 1922 C.E., his *Shradh* was performed according to the Hindu rites [— Sanyal, Sites Chandra, *His Highness late Maharaja Sir Jitendra Narayan Bhup Bahadur, K.C.S.I., Of Cooch Behar*, 1923, p. 9, also see — pp. 7-8 and p. 10] and no such monument was erected. During the Regency period (1922-1936 C.E.) of Maharani Indira Devi, the urns containing the sacred ashes were removed from the palace gardens on the 7th December, 1924 C.E. to the Keshub Ashram (popularly known as 'Rani Bagan', estd. 1889) and the monuments were re-erected therein [— *The Annual Administration Report Of The Cooch Behar State For The Year 1924-1925*, 1925, 2. General Administration, p. 34, para 122, 3. Revenue (Department), p. 9, para 31]. The Keshub Ashram, now consists of the memorials of Maharajas Nripendra Narayan, Raj Rajendra Narayan and Jagaddipendra Narayan; Nripendra's first and second daughters and fourth son — Maharajkumari Sukriti Sundari Devi, Maharajkumari Prativa Sundari Devi and Maharajkumar Hitendra Narayan, respectively. The memorial or monument of Sunity Devi lies at the premises of the Victoria Institution (College), 78 B, Acharya Profulla Chandra Road, Baithakkhana, Kolkata-9, bedside that of her father Brahmananda Keshav Chandra Sen. Though, the *Shradh* of Maharaja Jagaddipendra Narayan was performed according to the Hindu rites, but, his monument is to be found as mentioned already. The above information is noteworthy since, after the death of Kamala Devi, her ashes were immersed into the river Ganga, which is in contrary to the Brahmo tradition, but, usually in accordance with Hindu rites.

^{xiv} It is interesting to note that, out of the eight Banks established in Cooch Behar during the State period, there was a Private Bank named 'The Kamala Bank Ltd.'. Sometimes, it may become confusing because of the namesake of the Bank with Rani Kamala Devi and may persuade someone to conceive that the Bank was named after her. But, the Kamala Bank was established in the year 1929 C.E., when Rani Kamala Devi was only six to seven years of age and almost twelve years prior to her marriage with Maharakumar Indrajitendra Narayan and her formal relationship with Cooch Behar. Though, the reason of naming the Bank as 'Kamala' Bank is yet not known, but, it is beyond any doubt that the namesake is a mere coincidence. The Kamala Bank was amalgamated with the State Bank of India, probably on 12th January, 1967 C.E. [— Paul, Rzishikalpa, 'An Overview Of Banking System In Princely Cooch Behar', *The Historical Review*, January-June, July-December, 2021, {Number 1 & 2 (Combined)}, p. 39.]

^{xv} The 'Kamala Devi Girls School' was founded in 1943 C.E. During the early days of the present 'New Town Girls' High School (H.S.)', Cooch Behar, established on 17th March, 1952 C.E. (formal and official date: 1953 C.E.), its classes were held at Kamala Devi Girls School. At present, Kamala Devi Girls School (though Co-educational) is known as 'New Town Girls' Junior Basic School' and is located within the premises of New Town Girls' High School (H.S.). It appears, previously there was an endeavour to upgrade the School into a Higher Secondary Girls' School and the Education Department at Kolkata greatly wished to do so, but, owing to objection from certain locals and complete laxity on the part of the then Governing Body of the School it was never materialised. [— Dey, Krishnendu, 'Ekta Ful Fotar Kahini', *Arghya*, 1995; also see — Chattopadhyaya, Samir, 'Smarane, Bismarane' Bhaduri,

Bhabendra Chandra, 'Panchis Bachharer Ekti Itihas New Town Uccha Madhyamik Balika Vidyalaya', Chaudhury, Sudhir Chandra, 'Mone Pore', Dey (Sarkar), Sandhya, 'Vidyalayer Subarnajayanti', *Arghya*, 2003.] Non-availability of records makes it difficult to corroborate exactly when and why the name 'Kamala Devi Girls School' was changed to 'New Town Girls' Junior Basic School'.

^{xvi} This information is yet unsubstantiated.

^{xvii} It is interesting to note that there was a practice to name the State (Cooch Behar) Elephants after members of the Cooch Behar Royal dynasty. This practice also included the name of historical figure of the dynasty and family kin. We find a female Elephant "Kamala Devi", which undoubtedly was named after Rani Kamala Devi. Likewise, we find the tuskers "Chila Roy", "Jit Bahadur" and "Kaju Bahadur" named after Chila Roy or Shukladvaja, the great warrior of the Cooch Behar dynasty from the sixteenth century, Maharaja Jitendra Narayan and Major Rajendra Singh, Private Secretary to Maharaja Jagaddipendra Narayan of Cooch Behar who was popular as 'Kaku Mama' to the children of the family, respectively. Among the *Makhnas* – "Indrajit", after Maharajkumar Indrajitendra Narayan; among the other female Elephants — "Illa Devi", "Ayesha Devi", "Menaka Devi", "Uttara Devi" and "Devika Rani", after Maharajkumaris Illa Devi, Gayatri Devi (Ayesha) and Menaka Devi, Rajkumari Uttara Devi and Kumari Devika Devi, daughter of Illa Devi and Kumar Ramendra Kishore Dev Burma of Tripura, respectively. [— *Agreement Dated, the 28th August, 1949 Made Between The Governor General of India And His Highness the Maharaja Of Cooch Behar*, pp. 7-8; Cf. — Moore, *op. cit.*, p. 274.]

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Appendix-I:

Nani (Reminiscence of Bhawani Kumari Mahtab of Burdwan on Rani Kamala Devi):

My mother's mother or Nani as we called her, was very attractive, of medium height, very elegantly dressed in beautiful saris, her short hair was always well styled and hands always well-manicured. She was a moderate smoker and used long cigarette holders which made it all look so stylish! I once asked her what it felt like to smoke, and she said it was a wonderful, warm, roasty feeling and then asked me if I wanted a puff, I took a puff and of course coughed and spluttered and have never tried to smoke again! I think that was exactly what she wanted, wise lady! As a little girl, I loved watching her get ready, we had some of our best heart to heart conversations at these times. I too wanted to cut my long hair short like her, she then told me that she too used to have very long hair, however after she married, my grandfather's family (Cooch Behar Royal family) were all so stylish, so she too cut her hair short.

Some of my happiest times were the summer holidays that we spent with her in Madras (Chennai) and later, in Bangalore. My mother would take Bhai (Ijyaraj Singh, now His Highness the Maharao of Kotah) and me every summer, my father too would visit for some time. She was a doting grandmother in every way. She was a good cook, and would have all our favourite food made for us. She loved her non-vegetarian food, I think my brother and I have inherited that from her! She introduced me to the joy of eating *idlis* with *ghee* and sugar! She took us to restaurants and the club, indulged us in every way. We were sent to the Marina beach every evening to play. Looking back at those times, I think they were idyllic.

Nani was a warm affectionate person and had much love to give Bhai and me and we too returned it in full measure. She and my mother were very close, she absolutely doted on my mother. It was through Nani that an entirely different part of the country opened out for me. Everything was so different down south, the people, food, customs, language (I learnt to speak some Telugu) to what we were used to back home. Many decades later I took my younger daughter (Rajkumari Kriti Kumari Mahtab) down south, to both Hyderabad and Madras to meet some of my Pithapuram uncles and aunts and show her that world, and she loved it. It made me a less insular person, more accepting of different ways, this I think, helped me in settling down in Kolkata after my marriage in yet a different world.

Appendix-II:

Following are some Recipes from Rani Kamala Devi's Cook Book:

1. *Sakku Ooragai* (Green Mango Pickle):

25 green mangos (small ones),

3 cups mustard seeds, powdered,

3 cups rock salt, powdered,

3 cups chili powder (homemade),

1 cup peeled garlic,

2 tablespoons *haldi* (turmeric powder),

3 tablespoons *methi* seeds (fenugreek; roasted and powdered),

1 kg. *til* (sesame) oil.

Remove stones from mangos and throw away. Do not peel mangos. Cut mangos into small pieces. Mix everything together. Let it marinate for 2-3 days. It will not last longer than a month or two, so make a little at a time.

2. *Egg Pulusoo* (Egg Curry in *Jhol*):

Serves 5-6 people. *Pulusoo* is the *Telegu* word for *Jhol*/Liquid Gravy:

6 eggs,

150 gms. oil,

250 gms. onions (one onion cut in big pieces, the rest made into paste),

1 teaspoon mustard seeds,

1 teaspoon *methi* seeds,

4 green chillies slit half way,

3 curry leaves (*meethi patha*).

3 cloves garlic (half a clove peeled, the rest made into paste),

10 gms. ginger paste,

1/2 teaspoon *haldi*,

50 gms. *dhaniya* (coriander) powder,

25 gms. chili powder,

Salt to taste,

50 gms. tamarind/*imli* to be made into 6 cups tamarind water,

2 teaspoons *jeera* (cumin).

Boil the oil. Hard boil the eggs, notch them and fry them to a golden colour in the oil. Put eggs aside. In some oil put onion slices, mustard seeds and *methi* seeds and fry. Then add green chillies, curry leaves, onion paste, garlic paste and ginger paste and fry them. Add *haldi* powder, *dhaniya* powder and chili powder and fry well. Put in the salt and tamarind water and let it boil for a bit. Add eggs and let boil till curry thickens to required consistency. The half peeled garlic and the *jeera* should be crushed together and added to the curry. Boil for a minute or two and take it off the fire. The curry is ready.

3. Dark Fried Chicken:

Serves 4 people:

1 medium chicken, jointed,

300 gms. onions (1 tablespoon cut in pieces and the rest made into paste),

3 garlic cloves (1 clove whole and the rest made into paste),

25 gms. *khus khus* paste,

100 gms. *dhaniya* powder,

35 gms. chilly powder,

30 gms. ginger paste,

15 cloves/*laung/lavang*,

1 – inch cinnamon,

5 cardamoms,
1 teaspoon *haldi*,
250 gms. oil,
Salt to taste,
2 teaspoons *jeera*.

Mix the chicken well with all masalas except the 1 tablespoon onion pieces, the 1 whole garlic clove and the *jeera*. Add enough water and boil till chicken is 3/4 done. Boil the oil and fry the chicken pieces only. Take out the pieces and keep aside. In same oil put in onion pieces and fry well. Add masala and chicken and fry till dark, dry and done. Pound the clove of garlic with the *jeera* and add to the curry. Stir slightly and take off fire. There should be a bit of oil in the masala of the curry after it is done.

Note: There is no *jhol* in this curry. Nor is there thick masala. It is on the dry side with a little masala.

4. Mutton Korma:

Serves 4 people:

1 kg mutton cut into *botis* ('Boti' is the Hindi word for a cube of meat – the size of regular meat pieces in a meat curry. The size can be cut to whatever size one may wish),

300 gms. oil,
25 cloves/*laung/lavang*,
5 cardamom,
1 – inch cinnamon,
2 bay leaves/*tej patta*,
1/2 kg. onions, sliced,
25 gms. green chillies, slit half way,
50 gms. ginger paste,
4 garlic cloves, made into paste,
1 teaspoon *haldi*,

Salt to taste,

5 gms. *dhaniya* powder,

1/2 teaspoon chilly powder,

50 gms. cashew nut paste,

100 gms. *khus khus* paste,

500 gms. dahi/curds,

1/4 cup water.

Boil oil well. Put a little aside. In main oil put in cloves, cardamom, cinnamon and bay leaves and fry for a minute. Then add onions and green chillies and fry well. Add meat and fry for a while. Add ginger, garlic, *haldi* and salt and cook till meat is fried well. Add *dhaniya* powder and fry for 5 minutes. Add chilly powder and fry slightly. Then add the oil that was kept aside. Half the cashew nut paste and half the *khus khus* paste should be mixed in the *dahi* (curd) and kept aside. The rest of the cashew nut paste and *khus khus* paste should be mixed in the water, and then added to the frying mutton, and it should all be cooked till golden in colour. Add the *dahi* mixture and keep stirring (to avoid lumps). Cook till it is ready, meat is soft, and curry is of required consistency. It should have a thickish *jhol*.

Note: Chicken can be cooked the same way.

